

BEHAVIOR OF A DEPOLYABLE STRUCTURE WITH COMPOSITE TAPE-SRPNINGS

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SUMMARY: An innovative concept of a deployable boom made of composite tape-springs and novel flexible linear axis structural hinges (FLASH) is presented in this paper. The boom consists of periodic bay structures. Each bay structure has three longerons that are connected with battens. Diagonals can be added if higher torsional performance is required. The longerons are connected together with FLASH joints. The FLASH joint has two stable stages. The deployed stage is self-locking due to the curvature of the tape-spring longeron. In the stowed stage, the longerons are flattened. The structural performance of the boom including stiffness and strength was investigated by finite element analysis. It is found that the axial and bending strengths of the boom are comparable with other booms. The axial and flexural stiffnesses can be estimated only from the properties of the longerons. The battens or diagonals are not significant. The result also indicates that the ratio of bending strength and the product of axial strength and the effective radius of the boom is related to the shear support of the periodic bay structure.

KEYWORDS: deployable structures, composite tape-spring, numerical analysis.

INTRODUCTION

The growing demand of large space structures on orbit and the limitation of their sizes during launch propel the advancement of technologies on the development of structures with features of ultra-light weight and compact storage. Joint technology limitations are a significant barrier to achieving greater structural packaging efficiencies and larger structures. Solid rod elements have been used extensively in articulated deployable truss structures (space station solar array masts, Shuttle Radar Topography Mission mast). This predominance of solid rod elements is related to the ease with which such elements can be compactly hinged; ball and socket joints are typically used. The relatively small diameter of a solid rod allows small balls and accordingly, compact hinges. Correspondingly efficient hinge technologies for shell structures (tubes, tape-springs, etc.) have been more elusive. The technology presented here is unique in that it allows slit-tubes and other shell structures with significant structural depth to be flattened to a thickness on the order of the shell thickness and the folded. The boom technology investigated in this paper circumvents these limitations by employing truss elements with significant deployed depth and the ability to be flattened for a thin node stack height. An innovative concept of deployable structures is currently being pursued at the Air Force Research Laboratory (AFRL). It utilizes composite tape-springs and flexible linear axis structural hinges (FLASH) to achieve very high packing efficiency.

A deployable structure consisting of 6 bays is shown in Fig. 1. The deployable structure is made up of repetitive base-structures. The base-structures are jointed together with FLASH joints. Fig. 2 depicts the base-structure. As shown in the figure, two tape-springs are jointed together with the FLASH joint and form the longeron. These tape-springs can be flattened transversally and folded longitudinally. Their deformation is purely elastic. In the current design, the tape-spring is a 3-ply laminate. The outside plies are $\pm 45^\circ$ woven fabrics. The fiber of the middle ply is unidirectional and longitudinal. Woven fabrics are selected because they can withstand higher failure strain than that of unidirectional fibers [1]. The length of a tape-spring is 101.6 mm. The tape-spring has a circular cross-section with radius of 28.7 mm. It subtends an angle of 120° . The length of the batten is 206 mm. The batten can be flat composite laminate or has circular cross-section. The lay-up is similar to that of the tape-spring. Based on a previous feasibility study [2], the maximum strain in the stowed base-structure is lower than the failure strain of the material. In addition, the battens nest nicely in the stowed configuration. In this paper, we will investigate the structural behavior of this deployable structure with different configurations. The analyses are conducted by finite element method. The axial, flexural, torsional, and shear stiffnesses of the boom were obtained. The bulking modes and loads were also presented.

DECSMAR Boom Concept

The DECSMAR boom, shown in Fig. 1, is a light-weight and highly efficient packaging structure. It consists of several bays of substructures. The DECSMAR technology employs several advanced and innovative features to achieve unprecedented levels of packaging and mass efficiency. First, the FLASH joints are locally pre-loaded by their tensioned bands. This feature achieves zero-deadband and high stiffness, while maintaining low deployment friction. The feature is also highly scaleable to ultra-efficient slender structures since a diagonal pre-stress (which would reduce strength) is not required. A second unique feature of the boom is that the shell-like elements can carry portion of shear loading. These unique features will allow an articulated deployable structure that exhibits unprecedented packaging efficiency (due to thin hinge lines) and simplicity.

The periodic substructure, as shown in Fig. 2, is made of carbon-fiber reinforced epoxy tape-springs. They can be flattened transversally and folded longitudinally. The tape-spring deformation is purely elastic. Two tape-springs connected with FLASH joints form the longeron. The battens can have circular cross-sections similar to the longeron or be flat. The periodic substructures are then connected together with FLASH joints and form the boom.

FLASH JOINTS

The FLASH joint behaves like a piano hinge in that it is engineered to be highly flexible, but is also zero deadband (i.e. no free play in the hinge). The hinge axis flexibility allows for a locked configuration when the hinge axis is curved and a freely articulated configuration when the axis is straight. Fig. 3 shows this joint technology. The hinge axes are flexible to allow the tape-spring type of longerons to flex either concave or convex and not buckle the teeth of hinge or induce stress concentrations between the teeth. This flexibility feature is accommodated through the use of a tensioned rolling band device configured similar to what

is often called a rolamite joint. The rolamite device was invented by Donald F. Wilkes in 1967 and patented in 1969 and 1971 [3]. It incorporates a similar tensioned band in various configurations, but not in the form of a joint.

Fig. 1: A deployable structure with 6 bays

Fig. 2: The base structure

Fig. 3: FLASH joint technology (a) in the deployed/locked configuration and (b) in the flattened/package configuration

Work by Soykasap et al. [4] on tape-spring rolling hinges concentrated on continuous, elastic hinges that were self-deploying and self locked based on metal tape-springs and rolamite devices. Their work employed double tape-springs face-to-face (both concave sides facing) while the FLASH joint connects two tape-springs end-to-end. The current configuration, which is a free (no pins) joint, is most similar to a 1976 patent by Hillberry et al. [5] Their patent focused on a rolling contact joint with applications for prosthetic joints. In this instance two bodies were held in contact with tensioned bands which maintained the bodies in contact and gave the joint the desired movement (Fig. 4). The earliest known use of tensioned bands to synchronize the rotation of two pinned discs is by John Harrison in his 1728 maritime clock, the Harrison one (H1) [6, 7].

Fig. 4: Rolling band device configuration [5, 6]

The FLASH joint has two components: a tensioned band and teeth. The tensioned band winds in a reversing helical arrangement. Ideally, the band would be aligned with the tape spring's longitudinal axis. The tooth "line" gets broken up into discrete pieces along total length of the interface (perimeter of the longeron cross-section). The more teeth, the smaller they become, but the more curvature change they can accept as a whole system. Detailed description of the FLASH joint can be found in the article [2].

A typical tooth is shown in Fig. 5. The root of a tooth provides interfaces between the tooth and the longeron. There are two contact surfaces on the tooth for the deployed and stowed stages. In these limit states; the band is in lower tension states than during deployment. The arrangement also provides the ability to rotate with the changing shape of the longeron during deployment. The teeth maintain contact throughout the deployment, and not stress the longeron in either stowed (flat) or deployed (tape hinge) shape. Also, a bevel is added to the teeth to provide a flat contact area at the deployed state. The tooth provides enough of a bonding surface in order to maintain attachment to the longeron. There is enough surface area to transfer load, but not so much that with repeated deployments, the bond would break and the teeth become "loose" (no longer attached to the longeron, but held in place by the band).

A groove was put into the surface of a tooth to hold and control the band so it does not end up sliding along the interface line. This groove goes helically a full 360 degrees around each tooth. Because of the "reversing" direction of the band from longeron edge to longeron edge, this groove actually reverses pitch to create two directional types of teeth (left wind vs. right wind). This is the only differentiating factor between any teeth and thus keeps the manufacturing costs to a minimum (only two molds). The prototyped teeth made with DuraForm™ GF are shown in Fig. 6.

FINITE ELEMENT MODEL

Finite Element models are constructed to determine the structural performance of the DECSMAR booms. The tape-spring is made of 3-layer composite laminate. The outside plies are $\pm 45^\circ$ woven fibers. The fiber of the middle ply is unidirectional and longitudinal. Two tape-springs connected with FLASH joints form the longeron. The radius (ρ_L) of the circular cross section of the longeron is 29 mm. It subtends an angle (θ_L) of 120° . The thickness of the longeron (t_L) is 0.38 mm. The length of the batten is 206 mm. The batten has the same construction as that of longeron. When circular cross-section battens are used,

the radius is the same as the longeron. It subtends an angle of 60° . The stacking sequence and the properties of the composite laminate are shown in Tables 1 and 2, respectively.

Fig. 5: Solid model of FLASH tooth

Fig. 6: Rapid prototyped FLASH teeth

Table 1: Stacking sequence of the composite laminate

Layer	Material	Orientation	Thickness
1	Bi-directional fabric	$45^\circ/-45^\circ$	0.0635 mm
2	Unidirectional fabric	0°	0.254 mm
3	Bi-directional fabric	$45^\circ/-45^\circ$	0.0635 mm

Table 2: Properties of the reinforced carbon fiber materials

Material	E_{11} (Pa)	E_{22} (Pa)	ν_{12}	G_{12} (Pa)	G_{13} (Pa)	G_{23} (Pa)
Bi-directional fabric	8.73×10^{10}	8.73×10^{10}	0.0264	5.13×10^9	4.04×10^9	4.04×10^9
Unidirectional fabric	1.65×10^{11}	9.022×10^9	0.256	5.13×10^9	5.13×10^9	2.05×10^9

We have investigated the packaging of the boom and the maximum strain during folding in a previous study [2]. Nonlinear geometrically finite element analyses were conducted to fold the substructures with different configurations. We found that the maximum principal strain at stowed position of a boom with flat batten is about 1%. For this boom, the distance between the center of the batten and the bottom FLASH joint is 38.1 mm. The boom (Boom A) is shown in Fig. 7. A boom with battens having circular sections has also been analyzed. The maximum principal strain is found to be 1.3%. The boom (Boom B) is shown in Fig. 8. The length of the circular sections is about 101.6 mm. The distance between the center of the batten and the bottom FLASH joint is also 38.1 mm. Both booms can be compactly packed.

The structural performance of these two booms is carried out with ABAQUS. 4-node quadrilateral full integration general shell elements (S4) are used. They have six degrees of freedom at each node. To mimic the FLASH joints, associate nodes at different longerons are linked together using the multiple point constraint (MPC) option in ABAQUS. Only rotation in θ direction is permitted at these nodes. The nodes at the top of the boom were tied to an artificial node, located at the geometric center of the cross section, through rigid beam elements. Therefore, pure bending can be applied at the artificial node. The nodes at the bottom of the boom were fixed.

Fig. 7: Boom A with flat battens

Fig. 8: Boom B with circular-sectioned battens

RESULTS

The axial stiffness (EA), flexural stiffness (EI), torsional stiffness (GJ), and shear stiffness (GA) are determined. We also determine the strength including axial strength, torsion strength, and bending strength. The stiffness and strength of these two booms are shown in Tables 3 and 4, respectively. The axial and bending stiffnesses of these two booms are very similar as expected. They are dominated by the properties of longerons.

Table 3: Stiffness of the booms

	Boom A (with flat battens)	Boom B (with curve-section battens)
EA (MN)	10.3	10.3
EI (kN-m ²)	92.5	99.0
GJ (N-m ²)	81.69	543.4
GA (kN)	104.4	104.7

Table 4: Strength of the booms

	Boom A	Boom B
Axial (N)	2493	3370
Torsional (N-m)	11.6	17.7
Bending (N-m)	288.9	334.2

To examine the issue of EA and EI of the boom, let consider the boom is made of three continuous longerons as shown in Fig. 9. The axial material area of the three longerons is 69.42 mm² ($3 \cdot A_L = 3 \cdot \rho_L \cdot \theta_L \cdot t_L$). The average axial elastic modulus of the composite laminate is 139.1 GPa. The EA is 9.66 MN. The result is very similar to the finding by finite element analysis (EA = 10.3 MN).

The moment can be calculated as the sum of the product of the axial load of a longeron and the corresponding moment arm. By ignoring the moment of inertia of the longeron about the centroid of the cross section of a longeron, the moment of inertia about the x-axis is given by the formula:

$$I_x = \sum_{\substack{\text{longeron 3} \\ \text{longern } i=1}} A_L \left[R_c \sin \alpha_i + \frac{2 * \rho_L \sin \left(\frac{\theta_L}{2} \right) \sin \beta_i}{\theta_L} \right]^2 \quad (1)$$

Where R_c is the distance from the geometric center to the arc center of the longeron. Angles α_i and β_i are defined in Fig. 9. For this boom, $I_x = 6.987 \times 10^5 \text{ mm}^4$, $EI = 97.18 \text{ kN-m}^2$. Bending stiffness EI is estimated as 98.23 kN-m^2 by using the I_x proposed by Murphey [8]

$$I_x = \frac{9}{2} * A_L * R^2 \quad (2)$$

where R (effective radius) is the distance from the geometric center to the centroid of the cross section of the longeron. These two simple calculations agree well with the finite element result of Booms A and B (see Table 3).

Fig. 9: The cross-section of the boom with only the longerons

Let P_1 , P_2 , and P_3 be the axial loads at longerons 1, 2, and 3 be respectively. When an axial load (N) is applied, the load at each longeron is identical ($P_1 = P_2 = P_3 = N/3$). When a bending moment (M) is applied, the axial load at the longeron is assumed to be linear with the distance (y_i) between the centroid of the cross section of a longeron i and the x-axis. Since $y_2 = y_3 = 0.5 * y_1$, $P_2 = P_3 = 0.5 * P_1$. Bending moment about the x-axis is $M = 3 * P_2 * R$ (or $1.5 * P_1 * R$). If we assume the axial load of one longeron under buckling moment is the same as that under axial strength. That is $P_1 = N/3$ or $P_2 = N/3$. Then the ratio ($R_{fa} = M/N$) between flexural strength and axial strength is between $0.5 R$ and R .

The R_{fa} for Booms A and B are $0.1158 \text{ m} (= 0.81 R)$ and $0.099 \text{ m} (= 0.69 R)$, respectively. These numbers are within the range ($1/2 \sim 1$) that confirms the simple concept. As shown in Table 4, both M and N increase with increasing shear support. The improvement of N is more pronounced than that of M .

The deformation shapes of Booms A and B due to axial load and bending moment are depicted in Figs. 10 and 11. As shown in Fig. 10, for both booms the buckling modes due to axial load are a twisting type and not the typical Euler type. Buckling of battens is observed in Boom A (see Fig. 10a). Boom B having battens with circular cross-sections and no buckling is observed (see Fig. 10b). As shown in Fig. 11, the deformation shape due to bending moment is similar for both booms. The buckling shapes are due to the twisting of one longeron. It implies that the performance of the boom can be improved by increasing shear support. Thus, diagonals are added to Boom B to produce Boom C. The diagonals are composite laminate of 12.7 mm wide with thickness of 0.38 mm. It is made of unidirectional fibers with the properties as shown in Table 2. The configuration of the Boom C is depicted in Fig. 12. The finite element result of Boom C is shown in Table 5.

Fig. 10: The deformation shape due to axial load

Fig. 11: The deformation shape due to bending moment

Table 5: Stiffness and strength of Boom C

Stiffness				Strength		
EA	EI	GJ	GA	Axial	Torsion	Bending
10.3 MN	99.4 kN-m ²	3225.2 N-m ²	192.6 kN	4461 N	42.7 N-m	384.6 N-m

Fig. 12: Boom C with circular-sectioned battens and diagonals

As expected, very little improvement is found in EA and EI. The deformation shapes due to axial load and bending moment are shown in Fig. 13. The mode is still twisting. Significant improvement is found in GJ and GA. They are 5.9 and 1.8 times for GJ and GA over those of Boom B. R_{fa} of Boom C is 0.086 m (= 0.60 R) that is smaller than Boom B. A consistent trend is observed here that the ratio decreases with the increase of shear support of longerons. Although not shown in this paper, another run has been carried out with rigid diagonals. R_{fa} is found to be 0.0758 m (= 0.53 R). Therefore, R_{fa} can be used as an indicator to identify the degree of shear support of longerons. The buckling mode shapes due to the axial and bending loadings for the boom with rigid diagonals are still local twisting. Therefore, it is the geometry of the boom that prevents the development of Euler buckling mode. We conclude that the current geometry (bay length and arc length of the longeron) excludes the development of Euler buckling mode under axial and bending loading.

Fig. 13: The deformation shapes of Boom C due to (a) axial load and (b) bending moment

CONCLUSIONS

An innovative boom with FLASH joints has been introduced here. The boom has excellent packing characteristics. The elastic strain in the stowed structure is small. The structural performance of the booms was examined. The axial and bending characteristics of the boom are comparable with or exceed the performance of other booms. The axial and bending stiffnesses of the boom can be estimated based on the properties of the longerons. The axial and flexural stiffnesses estimated by the simple formulas are in good agreement with the finite element analysis. The deformation shapes of axial and bending buckling modes are local twisting of the longerons. Diagonals are added to the boom and the torsional characteristics of the boom significantly increased. The axial and bending strengths are also increased. Twisting typed buckling modes are still observed subjected to axial and bending loadings. Based on the buckling modes, the increase of axial and bending strengths is come from the increase of torsional stiffness. We conclude that due to the current configuration of the boom, Euler buckling mode cannot be developed. The influence of bay length of this boom will be investigated in the future. Fabrication of physical models of DECSMAR boom is currently underway. The physical structure will be tested and the result will be used to verify the numerical finding.

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